

Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Estimation of Atenolol and Amlodipine Besylate in Pharmaceutical Formulations

Marwan A. Hasan¹, Rebwar O. Hasan², Khalid F. Alrawi¹

¹Department of Chemistry, Collage of Science, Anbar University, Anbar, Iraq.

²Department of Chemistry, Collage of Science, Salahaddian University, Erbil, Iraq.

Email Address:

Correspondence should be addressed to Rebwar O. Hasan rebwar.hassan@su.edu.krd

Received: 11 Nov 2020, Revised: 15 Nov 2020, Accepted: 23 Nov 2020, Online: 26 Dec 2020

Abstract

The present study clarifies the development of accurate, selective, rapid, sensitive, and economic four spectrophotometric methods for the simultaneous estimation of Atenolol (ATE) and amlodipine besylate (AMB) in their binary mixtures and pharmaceutical products. This combination is widely used in the treatment of cardiovascular disorders. Three multivariate analysis techniques were developed based on the application of calibration prediction (artificial intelligence techniques) includes; Artificial Neural Network (ANN) (method 1), partial least squares (PLS) (method 2), Principal Component Regression (PCR) (method 3), in those methods the ATE and AMB were measured at 238nm and 240nm respectively. The multivariate models are designed using twenty-five mixes as a set of calibration and five mixes as a set of validation. The fourth method depends on the second derivative of ratio spectrum (DR2) as a validation method for all above techniques. The linearity of all methods was observed in the concentration ranges of 0.5- 30.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for ATE and 0.25- 28.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ for AMB. ANOVA test was achieved on the pharmaceutical sample at a 95% confidence level for paralleling ANN, PLS, PCR, and DR2. The Established techniques have been used to separate laboratory prepared mixes of ATE and AMB. These processes have been evaluated conferring to the ICH guidelines with regard to linearity, accuracy, precision, selectivity, and specificity and can be used for sequence ATE and AMB quality control analysis in their dosage forms.

Keywords: Spectrophotometric, Atenolol, Amlodipine Besylate, Cardiovascular Disease, Artificial Intelligence Techniques.

1. Introduction

One of the greatest familiar causes of morbidity and mortality in the globe is cardiovascular disease. Cardiovascular disease management is performed by

combining drugs in which each functional with various mechanisms of achievement to get the therapy target (1,2). Atenolol (RS)-4-(2-hydroxy-3-isopropylaminopropoxy)

phenylacetamide is an antihypertensive drug acting as a P-adrenoceptor antagonist and It is a beta-1 blocker is mainly a medicinal drug used to treat various heart disorders such as cardiac arrhythmia and myocardial infarction(3) Thus its appropriate therapy to lower blood pressure(4). Amlodipine besylate (AMB) (3-ethyl-5-methyl (±)-2-((2-aminoethoxy)methyl)-4-(2chlorophenyl)-1,4 dihydro-6-methyl-

3,5pyridinedicarboxylatemonobenzenesulpho nate) belongs to class of dihydropyridine which, belong to third generation of calcium channels blockers (CCBs) drugs for treat cardiovascular diseases^(5,6). AMB is lowering the cytosolic free calcium concentration by blocking calcium pass into cells by blocking calcium cell receptor thus, AMB has a clear effect on the relaxing and contracting smooth

muscles in the body⁽⁷⁾. On that basis, these drugs act as a blood pressure regulator⁽⁸⁾. Analytically, applications of spectrometric methods in combing with ANN, PLS and PCR for the determination of multi-component substances have been reported⁽⁹⁻¹¹⁾. This approach also has been tested by a number of researchers as a valuable technique. On the other hand, A few methods are available for the simultaneous determination of ATE and AMB in combination; RP-HPLC⁽¹²⁾, HPTLC^(13, 14) and spectrophotometry^(15, 16).

The goal of this work was to develop four sensitive, precise, accurate, reliable, quick and cost-effective spectrophotometric methods for the determination of both drugs without previous separation.

ATO

AMB

Fig1. Chemical structure of Atenolol and Amlodipine Besylate⁽¹⁷⁾

2. Artificial Intelligence Techniques

Over the last decade, there has been a growing interest in using artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to analyze and interpret biological or genetic information, drug estimation, accelerate the development of drugs, and recognize selective petite molecular modulators or singular molecules and predict their performance. Development of robotic workflows and databanks to rapidly analyze large quantities of records and artificial neural networks (ANNs) for the improvement of new hypo-models and management strategies, forecast of syndrome development and assessment of drug

candidates, pharmacological reports may suggestively improve behavior outcomes⁽¹⁸⁾.

2.1. Artificial neural networks (ANNs) method

The artificial neural networks (ANNs) are centered on artificial intelligence (AI) technologies⁽¹⁹⁾. They are a computer model that activates the human brain, simple and nonlinear learning. Due to its high performance and strong prediction for nonlinear structures, it is an effective method of chemometry^(20, 21). In this study, multilayer back-propagation network was applied because it is the most common network manner⁽²²⁾.

2.2. Multivariate Methods

Multivariate spectral calibration is the typical method used for spectral calibration. Carrying out the quantifiable spectral analysis. Among many of the different regression methods for multivariate calibration, these methods are based on variable analysis such as partial least squares regression (PLS) and principal component regression (PCR) which is significant in chemometrics. PLS is a quantifiable spectral rottenness method that is close to PCR⁽²³⁻²⁵⁾. Recently, a quantifiable chemometric technique, PLS and PCR have been deeply involved in the interest of researchers at a rapid pace.

2.3. Derivative spectrophotometry method

Derivative spectrophotometry was commonly used for the estimation of drugs in multi-component systems with overlapping spectra, eliminating interference with matrix composition using zero-crossing techniques, there is more than one type of orders from derivative spectrophotometry first, second, third and fourth orders^(26, 27). In the present study, using a second derivative spectrophotometric method (DR²) with extreme sensitivity, selectivity and accuracy for the simultaneous assessment of ATE and AMB in pure form and in their therapeutic form.

3. Experimental

3.1. Instruments

A UV-visible spectrophotometer double beam (SHIMADZU, Japan) model UV-1800 PC with quartz cell match pair of 1cm path length was used and connected to Lenovo laptop. The used software was UV-Probe spectroscopy software edition 2.32.

3.2. Software

XL-STATA software for using the processing of ANN as well as PLS and PCR.

Additionally, Excel 2013 was useful for calculations and the signal transforms.

3.3. Material and chemicals

Atenolol (ATE) and Amlodipine besylate (AMB) were helpfully provided by pioneer company for the pharmaceutical industry, Iraq. Its purity was labeled to be 99.93% and 99.92%, respectively. The Pharmaceutical dosage was supplied Vasopin-AT Long Last medicines batch No. 41-4-VAS.C from Vasolife Healthcare - PCD Pharma Franchise Company- India. Each tablet is marked to contain 5 mg of AML and 25 mg of ATE. Methanol HPLC grade was acquired from Fischer, UK, as a solvent.

3.4. Standard solutions (stock and working)

0.1g of each of ATE and AMB were precisely balanced and transmitted into two different 100-mL volumetric flasks, 50 mL of methanol was added to each flask and shaken to dissolve. Then the volume was completed to the mark with methanol. Ten mL of both of ATE and AMB stock standard solutions were accurately moved into two distinct 100-mL volumetric flasks, then the volume was completed to the mark with methanol to obtain 1000 µg/mL concentration from both drugs. To pharmaceutical solutions formulation, twenty tablets were weighted, and fine powdered. Transferred in 100 mL volumetric flask to an equivalent weight of one tablet, Added 70 mL of methanol and socketed for 15 min, And the solution was then filtered and made to the mark with methanol. To achieve the concentrations of both products, the solution was diluted with methanol. All solutions are stable when stored in a refrigerator at about 4 ° C for a duration of 3 days.

4. Procedures

4.1. Spectral features of ATO and AMB

Aliquots equivalent to 100 μg for each of ATE and AMB were moved completely and separate from their standard working solutions (100 μg / mL) to 10-mL volumetric flasks. The volume was completed by methanol to obtain 10 μg / mL of ATE and AMB. Both drugs were dissolved with methanol under the same conditions because these drugs are very difficult to dissolve in water. Whereas, the effect of using methanol as a solvent on the spectrum shift is negligible compared to the other spectral references ⁽²⁸⁾. The spectrum absorption were recorded over the wavelength range of 190-380 nm.

4.2. Preparation of laboratory mixes

Thirty laboratory mixes were made randomly from standard stock solutions in various concentrations. These mixes could study the validation of the suggested methods.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Spectrum description

The absorbance spectrum of ATE and AMB over the range of 190–380 nm in methanol are confirmed. The UV spectrum of both drugs are powerfully interrelated with each other **fig.2**. The technique of UV – Vis spectrophotometry cannot be used to measure these drugs simultaneously. In this report, the ANN method was offered to overcome this problem that was coupled with the spectrophotometry method. Correspondingly, multivariate calibration methods such as PLS, PCR and DR² were used as proportional methods.

5.2. Calibration Curve of ATE and AMB

Standard solutions of ATE and AMP were freshly obtained in the concentration range of 0.5-30 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 0.25–28 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively by diluting the stock solutions, to obtained linearity, carve **fig 3**, **fig 4** shown the spectrum curves of ATE and AMB (0.5- 30.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, 0.25- 28.0 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) respectively, by using DR² method.

Fig.2. The spectrum absorption of ATE and AMB 10 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Fig.3. Calibration Curves and spectrum of ATE and AMB

Table. 1 Calibration data of ATE and AMB

drugs	Registration Equ.	R ²	Lamda max
ATE	$y = 0.0327x + 0.0007$	0.9998	224 nm
AMP	$y = 0.0303x - 0.0008$	0.9999	239.2 nm

A.DR2 method spectrum curves of ATE

B. DR² method spectrum curves of AMB

Fig.4 the spectrum curves A.B of ATE and AMB ($0.5- 30.0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, $0.25- 28.0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) respectively, by using DR² method

Table. 2 Achieved recovery and RMSE by usage of the ANN method in laboratory mixes.

Model no.	Real (µg/mL)		Predicted (µg/mL)		Recovery (%)	
Exp. data	ATE	AMB	ATE	AMB	ATE	AMB
1	3	2.8	3.015	2.801	100.496	100.034
2	21	2.8	20.982	2.799	99.9135	99.9578
3	3	19.6	3.040	19.603	101.327	100.013
4	3	2.8	3.075	2.805	102.487	100.172
5	1.5	1.4	1.482	1.399	98.8092	99.9171
6	25.5	1.4	25.506	1.400	100.025	100.029
7	1.5	23.8	1.503	23.800	100.233	100.000
8	1.5	1.4	1.581	1.413	105.428	100.941
9	1.5	1.4	1.501	1.400	100.082	100.005
10	1.5	22.4	1.457	22.397	97.1397	99.9875
11	6	5.6	6.044	5.604	100.738	100.067
12	12	5.6	11.988	5.585	99.8981	99.7329
13	6	11.2	5.984	11.189	99.7305	99.9054
14	4.5	2.8	4.483	2.762	99.6112	98.6459
15	19.5	2.8	19.507	2.798	100.038	99.9305
16	4.5	18.2	4.452	18.200	98.9332	100.000
17	3	4.2	3.002	4.203	100.069	100.070
18	9	16.8	9.066	16.844	100.738	100.260
19	1.5	8.4	1.498	8.400	99.8803	100.004
20	18	1.4	18.289	1.401	101.605	100.080
21	1.5	8.4	1.505	8.389	100.358	99.8697
22	10.5	4.2	10.610	4.197	101.045	99.9303
23	10.5	9.8	10.524	9.800	100.226	100.001
24	4.5	9.8	4.489	9.816	99.7453	100.165
25	4.5	4.2	4.561	4.211	101.348	100.269
average recovery					100.396	99.9994
RMSE					0.07096	0.01332
Validation data						
26	4.2	8.5	4.201	8.503	100.022	100.03
27	5.6	5.8	5.600	5.806	99.9985	100.101
28	2.2	11.5	2.200	11.499	100.018	99.995
29	10.5	8.6	10.49	8.598	99.9761	99.972
30	6.5	26.5	6.501	26.495	100.012	99.983
average recovery					100.005	100.016
RMSE					0.00125	0.00366

5.3. The ANN model⁽²⁹⁾

Artifice neural networks (ANN) was managed to predict the number of modules in thirty laboratory mixes. In this network, 2 And 5 layers thru 2, 3, 5, 7, and 9 neurons in all layers were utilized to predict the

concentration of ATE and AMB drugs. The greatest number of neurons was chosen in every layers built on the lowermost mean square error (MSE). The equation of MSE Was depleted according to the following:

$$MSE = 1/N \sum_{i=1}^n (y_{pred} - y_{obs})^2$$

Where y_{pred} and y_{obs} are the estimate predicted and the actual output, respectively.

Moreover, the recovery (%), the average recovery (%), and root mean squared error (RMSE) were computed and reviewed in **table 2**. This technique has an excellent power for calculating concentrations of ATE and AMB. The root square error (RMSE) which can be articulated as:

$$RMSE = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(y_{pred} - y_{obs})^2}{n} \right]^{1/2}$$

Where the sample y_{pred} its estimated value, y_{obs} is the actual sample value and n is the sample number⁽³⁰⁾.

Table. 3 Achieved recovery and RMSE by usage of the PLS method in laboratory mixes.

Sample no.	Real (µg/mL)		Predicted (µg/mL)		Recovery (%)	
	ATE	AMB	ATE	AMB	ATE	AMB
Exp. data						
1	3	2.8	3.002	2.841	100.067	101.472
2	21	2.8	20.880	2.826	99.4281	100.925
3	3	19.6	2.913	19.561	97.1080	99.8013
4	3	2.8	3.080	2.815	102.654	100.537
5	1.5	1.4	1.538	1.407	102.524	100.487
6	25.5	1.4	25.404	1.466	99.6226	104.722
7	1.5	23.8	1.520	23.562	101.308	99.000
8	1.5	1.4	1.507	1.439	100.467	102.781
9	1.5	1.4	1.507	1.393	100.493	99.4809
10	1.5	22.4	1.553	22.870	103.551	102.109
11	6	5.6	6.127	5.681	102.123	101.446
12	12	5.6	12.048	5.584	100.396	99.7106
13	6	11.2	6.105	11.134	101.753	99.4083
14	4.5	2.8	4.642	2.839	103.150	101.383
15	19.5	2.8	19.456	2.825	99.7764	100.883
16	4.5	18.2	4.586	18.059	101.909	99.2264
17	3	4.2	3.142	4.197	104.729	99.9324
18	9	16.8	9.092	16.616	101.017	98.9024
19	1.5	8.4	1.546	8.349	103.068	99.3880
20	18	1.4	17.964	1.458	99.7986	104.165
21	1.5	8.4	1.564	8.423	104.253	100.272
22	10.5	4.2	10.480	4.225	99.8080	100.600
23	10.5	9.8	10.548	9.816	100.457	100.164
24	4.5	9.8	4.567	9.801	101.487	100.018
25	4.5	4.2	4.651	4.219	103.347	100.455
Average recovery					101.371	100.687
RMSE					0.08175	0.1204
Validation data						
26	4.2	8.5	4.206	4.206	100.142	100.023
27	5.6	5.8	5.533	5.596	99.9285	100.103
28	2.2	11.5	2.201	2.201	100.045	99.9130
29	10.5	8.6	1.469	10.487	99.8761	99.8720
30	6.5	26.5	6.498	6.498	99.9692	99.9584
Average recovery					99.992	99.974
RMSE					0.00672	0.00874

5.4. Multivariate Methods ⁽³¹⁾

Using PLS and PCR techniques for the simultaneous estimation of ATE and AMB, 30 laboratory mixes were chosen for the guidance set (calibration set) and the test set for the validation set (prediction set) respectively. In order to verify the optimal number of modules. **Table 3,4** The recovery (%), the Average recovery (%), and RMSE of 30 laboratory mixes were measured by PLS and PCR methods, respectively. PLS method shows is better than PLC method for the

simultaneous determination of ATE and AMB.

5.5. DR² spectrophotometry method

The DR² method was behaved as the reference method **fig 4**. The results obtained by evaluating the market tablet using reference and chemo- metric methods with three measures are reported in Mean recovery results (percent) and (RSEM) for the ANN method are superior than the PLS and PCR methods, and the PLS is superior than the PCR method. **fig 5**.

Table. 4 Achieved recovery and RMSE by usage of the PCR method in laboratory mixes.

Sample no. Exp. data	Real (µg/mL)		Predicted (µg/mL)		Recovery (%)	
	ATE	AMB	ATE	AMB	ATE	AMB
1	3	2.8	3.045	2.822	101.496	100.800
2	21	2.8	21.192	2.797	100.913	99.8831
3	3	19.6	3.072	20.359	102.388	103.870
4	3	2.8	3.103	2.833	103.420	101.187
5	1.5	1.4	1.467	1.413	97.8102	100.905
6	25.5	1.4	25.706	1.413	100.808	100.929
7	1.5	23.8	1.541	24.009	102.703	100.880
8	1.5	1.4	1.583	1.470	105.550	104.981
9	1.5	1.4	1.512	1.425	100.780	101.805
10	1.5	22.4	1.442	22.618	96.1087	100.975
11	6	5.6	6.173	5.699	102.880	101.767
12	12	5.6	11.986	5.586	99.8874	99.7414
13	6	11.2	5.942	11.309	99.0320	100.975
14	4.5	2.8	4.662	2.790	103.602	99.6441
15	19.5	2.8	20.268	2.882	103.938	102.915
16	4.5	18.2	4.406	18.202	97.9022	100.009
17	3	4.2	3.105	4.246	103.503	101.090
18	9	16.8	9.146	17.014	101.622	101.274
19	1.5	8.4	1.498	8.475	99.8341	100.888
20	18	1.4	18.663	1.471	103.685	105.089
21	1.5	8.4	1.485	8.368	99.0112	99.6154
22	10.5	4.2	10.809	4.167	102.945	99.2208
23	10.5	9.8	11.055	9.764	105.286	99.6321
24	4.5	9.8	4.489	10.014	99.7654	102.187
25	4.5	4.2	4.561	4.217	101.365	100.414
Average recovery					101.449	101.227
RMSE					0.25678	0.18013
Validation data						
26	4.2	8.5	4.214	8.503	100.325	100.030
27	5.6	5.8	5.602	5.864	100.032	101.101
28	2.2	11.5	2.231	11.460	101.428	99.6547
29	10.5	8.6	10.49	8.594	99.9236	99.9275
30	6.5	26.5	6.566	26.476	101.012	99.9113
Average recovery					100.544	100.124
RMSE					0.03337	0.03536

The proposed methods showed excellent sensitivity, accuracy, and good linear range compared to other analytical methods **table 5** shown the result of analyzing of the proposed methods compare with other analytical methods

Methods	Drugs	proposed methods			Other methods			Ref.
		Linearity µg mL ⁻¹	Recover (%)	RSD (%)	Linearity µg mL ⁻¹	Recover (%)	RSD (%)	
ANN	ATE	0.5-30	100.05	0.01860	5-10	100.108	0.388	[32]
	AMB	0.25-28	100.016	0.05216	5-30	99.794	0.943	
PLS	ATE	0.5-30	99.992	0.10404	1-5	99.772	0.7890	[33]
	AMB	0.25-28	99.974	0.09141	5-25	100.092	0.7712	
PCR	ATE	0.5-30	100.544	0.64752	10- 19	99.78	1.06	[34]
	AMB	0.25-28	100.124	0.56220	10-30	100.19	0.763	[35]

Fig.5 compare the RSEM test results obtained from ANN, PLS and PCR methods for ATE and AMB

The above figure shows an exceptional accurate for the ANN method compare with PLS and PCR. The ANN method demonstrates a wide range of data in UV analysis ⁽³⁶⁾, in other side ANN depends directly on the spectrum weighted of the drug without any interference, as the digital spectrum value is directly proportional to the drug concentration. However, the other two methods PLS and PCR depend on the matrix

value of the spectrum data in X vs Y axis's ⁽³⁷⁾

5.6. Analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form

Applied DR² method as a reference method, that compares with another (AI) methods ANN, PLS and PCR. Analysis commercial form Vasopin-AT table contained 25 and 5 mg from ATE and AMB, respectively. The obtained results by analyzing the commercial

tablet from reference and (AI) methods with three measurements are reviewed in **Table 6**. The results of the Average recovery (%) and RSD (%) for the ANN method are superior

than the PLS and PCR methods, as well as the PLS is superior than the PCR. The three methods were more closely results in the reference method.

Table 6. Results of analyzing commercial tablets by proposed methods. Vasopin-AT label: 25 mg ATE and 5 mg AMB in each tablet.

method	ATE				AMB			
	ANN	PLS	PCR	DR ²	ANN	PLS	PCR	DR ²
Found (mg) ^a	24.84	24.89	24.98	24.78	5.044	4.979	5.105	5.047
Recover (%)	99.35	99.57	99.93	99.13	100.8	99.59	102.1	100.9
RSD (%)	0.206	0.362	0.575	0.363	0.238	0.249	0.443	0.431

^a Mean value of the three measurements

5.7. ANOVA test

ANOVA test was achieved on the marker sample at a 95% confidence level for matching ANN, PLS, PCR, and DR² as a reference techniques. The results are described in **Table 7**. There is no significant variance concerning these techniques because calculated F-values are less than the critical F-values.

Table 7. ANOVA results in one-way implementation of the methods suggested to the pharmaceutical dosage form.

Source of Variation	SS	df ^a	MS	F calculated	F critical
Between groups					
ATE	1.0532	3	0.3511	2.2200	4.066181
AMB	9.497	3	3.1656	2.46158	4.066180
Within groups					
ATE	1.2650	8	0.1581		
AMB	1.029	8	0.1286		
Total					
ATE	2.3182	11			
AMB	10.526	11			

SS, summation of squares; df, degree unit of freedom; MS, mean squares. ^a Degree of freedom for between groups: h-1; Within Groups: h (n-1); Total: hn-1; h, number of methods; n, number of samples of each method.

6. Conclusion

Generally, the simultaneous analysis of the current components in a mixture is significant due to the high importance of it in quality control. In mixes with high spectrum overlying, the ANN, PLS, and PCR techniques can be used with great accuracy. Considering all the results, it can be concluded that it is possible to use these methods for simultaneous quantitative analysis of the mixtures and real sample.

Also, the suggested techniques present satisfactory recovery ratios for components. In addition, these methods have been validated against the DR² method as an authentication method. R² and RMSE indicate that the ANN, PLS and as well as the PCR method have better results in prediction. Corresponding to ANOVA test, there is no significant variance between the suggested methods and the DR² as a reference method with a 95% confidence level. On the other

side, the suggested methods are simple, fast, economical, and there are no need prior separation steps that can be behaved as a powerful controlling tool for indication processing and simplification in analytical chemistry, its related divisions and as an appropriate tool for quality control laboratory.

7. References

- [1]. Howland, R. D., Mycek, M. J., Harvey, R. A., & Champe, P. C. (2006). *Lippincott's illustrated reviews: Pharmacology* (pp. 159-171). Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- [2]. Jukema, J. W., & van der Hoorn, J. W. (2004). Amlodipine and atorvastatin in atherosclerosis: a review of the potential of combination therapy. *Expert opinion on pharmacotherapy*, 5(2), 459-468.
- [3]. Khairy, M., Khorshed, A. A., Rashwan, F. A., Salah, G. A., Abdel-Wadood, H. M., & Banks, C. E. (2017). Simultaneous voltammetric determination of antihypertensive drugs nifedipine and atenolol utilizing MgO nanoplatelet modified screen-printed electrodes in pharmaceuticals and human fluids. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, 252, 1045-1054.
- [4]. SC, S. (2002). *Martindale. The complete drug reference*, 36, 3694.
- [5]. Grossman, E., & Messerli, F. H. (2004). Calcium antagonists. *Progress in cardiovascular diseases*, 47(1), 34-57
- [6]. De Paoli, P., Cerbai, E., Koidl, B., Kirchengast, M., Sartiani, L., & Mugelli, A. (2002). Selectivity of different calcium antagonists on T-and L-type calcium currents in guinea-pig ventricular myocytes. *Pharmacological research*, 46(6), 491-497
- [7]. Ozawa, Y., Hayashi, K., & Kobori, H. (2006). New generation calcium channel blockers in hypertensive treatment. *Current hypertension reviews*, 2(2), 103-111.
- [8]. Ananchenko, G., Novakovic, J., & Lewis, J. (2012). Amlodipine besylate. In *Profiles of Drug Substances, Excipients and Related Methodology* (Vol. 37, pp. 31-77). Academic Press
- [9]. Zhang, C. H., Yun, Y. H., Zhang, Z. M., & Liang, Y. Z. (2016). Simultaneous determination of neutral and uronic sugars based on UV-vis spectrometry combined with PLS. *International journal of biological macromolecules*, 87, 290-294.
- [10]. Devrim, B., Dinc, E., & Bozkir, A. S. U. M. A. N. (2014). Fast determination of diphenhydramine hydrochloride in reconstitutable syrups by CWT, PLS and PCR methods. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica-Drug Research*, 71(5), 721-729.
- [11]. Dinç, E., Baleanu, D., Ioele, G., De Luca, M., & Ragno, G. (2008). Multivariate analysis of paracetamol, propiphenazone, caffeine and thiamine in quaternary mixtures by PCR, PLS and ANN calibrations applied on wavelet transform data. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 48(5), 1471-1475.
- [12]. Barman, R. K., Islam, M. A., Ahmed, M., Wahed, M. I., Islam, R., Khan, A., ... & Rahman, B. M. (2007). Simultaneous high-performance liquid chromatographic determination of atenolol and amlodipine in pharmaceutical-dosage form. *Pak. J. Pharm. Sci*, 20(4), 274-279.
- [13]. Argekar, A. P., & Powar, S. G. (2000). Simultaneous determination of atenolol and amlodipine in tablets by high-performance thin-layer chromatography. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 21(6), 1137-1142.
- [14]. Kannappan, V., & Mannemala, S. S. (2016). Simultaneous enantioseparation and purity determination of chiral switches of amlodipine and atenolol by liquid chromatography. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 120, 221-227.
- [15]. Rathee, P., Rathee, S., Thakur, S., & Kumar, V. (2010). Simultaneous Estimation of Amlodipine Besylate and Atenolol as API and in Tablet Dosage Forms by Vierodt's Method using UV Spectrophotometry. *International Journal of ChemTech Research*, 2(1), 62-68.
- [16]. Lamie, N. T. (2015). Simultaneous determination of binary mixture of amlodipine besylate and atenolol based on dual wavelengths. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 149, 201-207.
- [17]. Lamie, N. T. (2015). Simultaneous determination of binary mixture of amlodipine besylate and atenolol based on dual wavelengths. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 149, 201-207.
- [18]. Hassanzadeh, P., Atyabi, F., & Dinarvand, R. (2019). The significance of artificial intelligence in drug delivery system design. *Advanced drug delivery reviews*, 151, 169-190.

- [19]. Khodaveisi, J., Dadfarnia, S., Shabani, A. M. H., Moghadam, M. R., & Hormozi-Nezhad, M. R. (2015). Artificial neural network assisted kinetic spectrophotometric technique for simultaneous determination of paracetamol and p-aminophenol in pharmaceutical samples using localized surface plasmon resonance band of silver nanoparticles. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 138, 474-480.
- [20]. Ghaedi, A. (2015). Simultaneous prediction of the thermodynamic properties of aqueous solution of ethylene glycol monoethyl ether using artificial neural network. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 207, 327-333.
- [21]. Hasani, M., & Moloudi, M. (2008). Application of principal component-artificial neural network models for simultaneous determination of phenolic compounds by a kinetic spectrophotometric method. *Journal of hazardous materials*, 157(1), 161-169.
- [22]. Tashkhourian, J., Hormozi-Nezhad, M. R., & Khodaveisi, J. (2011). Application of silver nanoparticles and principal component-artificial neural network models for simultaneous determination of levodopa and benserazide hydrochloride by a kinetic spectrophotometric method. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 82(1), 25-30.
- [23]. Khajehsharifi, H., Eskandari, Z., & Sareban, N. (2017). Using partial least squares and principal component regression in simultaneous spectrophotometric analysis of pyrimidine bases. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 10, S141-S147.
- [24]. Khajehsharifi, H., Pourbasheer, E., Tavallali, H., Sarvi, S., & Sadeghi, M. (2017). The comparison of partial least squares and principal component regression in simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of ascorbic acid, dopamine and uric acid in real samples. *Arabian Journal of Chemistry*, 10, S3451-S3458.
- [25]. Aleixandre-Tudo, J. L., Nieuwoudt, H., Aleixandre, J. L., & Du Toit, W. J. (2015). Robust ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) partial least-squares (PLS) models for tannin quantification in red wine. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 63(4), 1088-1098.
- [26]. Bobrowska-Grzesik, E. (2001). Determination of amoxicillin and clavulanic acid in some pharmaceutical preparations by derivative spectrophotometry. *Microchimica Acta*, 136(1-2), 31-34.
- [27]. Vetuschi, C., Giannandrea, A., Carlucci, G., & Mazzeo, P. (2005). Determination of hydrochlorothiazide and irbesartan in pharmaceuticals by fourth-order UV derivative spectrophotometry. *Il Farmaco*, 60(8), 665-670.
- [28]. Ritschel, W. A. (1981). Book Review: UV and IR Spectra of Some Important Drugs.
- [29]. Kamble, V. B., & Deshmukh, S. N. (2019). Comparison Between Accuracy and MSE, RMSE by Using Proposed Method with Imputation Technique. *Oriental Journal of Computer Science and Technology*, 10(4), 773-779.
- [30]. Kasture, A. V., & Ramteke, M. (2006). Simultaneous UV-spectrophotometric method for the estimation of atenolol and amlodipine besylate in combined dosage form. *Indian journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 68(3).
- [31]. Dinç, E., Baleanu, D., Ioele, G., De Luca, M., & Ragno, G. (2008). Multivariate analysis of paracetamol, propiphenazone, caffeine and thiamine in quaternary mixtures by PCR, PLS and ANN calibrations applied on wavelet transform data. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis*, 48(5), 1471-1475.
- [32]. Attia, K. A. S. M., Nassar, M. W., & Abolmagd, E. (2016). Simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of amlodipine and atenolol in pharmaceutical preparations using chemometric techniques. *ACAIJ*, 16(5), 205-210.
- [33]. Ferraro, M. C., Castellano, P. M., & Kaufman, T. S. (2004). Chemometric determination of amiloride hydrochloride, atenolol, hydrochlorothiazide and timolol maleate in synthetic mixtures and pharmaceutical formulations. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis*, 34(2), 305-314.
- [34]. Mohamed, N. G. (2011). Simultaneous determination of amlodipine and valsartan. *Analytical chemistry insights*, 6, ACI-S7282.
- [35]. Hassoun, M. H. (1995). *Fundamentals of artificial neural networks*. MIT press.
- [36]. Bourquin, J., Schmidli, H., van Hoogevest, P., & Leuenberger, H. (1998). Advantages of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) as alternative modelling technique for data sets showing non-linear relationships using data from a galenic study on a solid dosage form. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 7(1), 5-16.
- [37]. Karimi, M. A., Ardakani, M. M., Behjatmanesh-Ardakani, R., Nezhad, H. R. M., & Amiryan, H. (2008). Individual and simultaneous determinations of phenothiazine

- drugs using PCR, PLS and (OSC)-PLS multivariate calibration methods. *Journal of the Serbian Chemical Society*, 73(2), 233-247.
- [38]. Zainab J. Sweah & Ahmed J. Mohammed. (2020). Preparation and Study of Mechanical and Thermal Properties of Polymer Blends from Recycled Materials of Polystyrene and Polymethylmethacrylate with Different Ratio of Diethylmalonate. *Journal of Global Scientific Research*. Vol. 4. Pp:466-476.
- [39]. Ahmed Hachim Sultan Al – Dulaimi & Salwa Abdul-Satar Jabbar. (2019). Synthesis and Characterization of Some 3-chloro-azitidine-3-on Compounds of the 2-amino Pyrimidine Compound and Evaluation of their Biological Activity. *Journal of Global Scientific Research*. Vol. 2. Pp: 199-217.